

Appendix A: Modelling hyperparameter details

This appendix lists the search spaces and selected hyperparameters for the three modelling methods (PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR) applied in this study. All parameters were determined by five-fold cross-validation on the calibration set, separately for each soil-depth model and for the integrated model. The selected values are those reported in Sect. 2.7 and are reproduced here in full to support reproducibility.

Table A1. Number of latent variables selected by leave-one-out cross-validation for each PLSR model. The candidate range was 1 to 20 components (bounded above by $n-2$ calibration samples or the number of available bands).

Model	Depth	n components selected	Cal. R^2	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE (g kg^{-1})
PLSR	0–20 cm	4	0.326	0.148	1.795
PLSR	20–40 cm	6	0.557	0.156	0.947
PLSR	40–60 cm	1	0.087	0.026	0.660
PLSR	60–80 cm	1	0.016	-0.014	0.638
PLSR	Integrated	8	0.704	0.712	1.641

A.1 Partial least squares regression (PLSR)

PLSR was implemented using the NIPALS algorithm with leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV) to select the optimal number of latent variables. Candidate values ranged from 1 to 20 components. The number of components minimising the cross-validated root mean squared error of prediction (RMSECV) was selected for each model. Selected components differed substantially among models (Table A1), reflecting differences in calibration-set complexity: deeper layers with narrow SOC range required only a single component, while the integrated model used eight.

A.2 Grid-search support vector regression (GRID-SVR)

GRID-SVR used a radial-basis-function (RBF) kernel. The penalty C and kernel-width γ were searched on a logarithmically spaced grid:

- $C \in [10^{-2}, 10^4]$, 13 candidate values: $10^{-2}, 10^{-1.5}, 10^{-1}, 10^{-0.5}, 10^0, 10^{0.5}, 10^1, 10^{1.5}, 10^2, 10^{2.5}, 10^3, 10^{3.5}, 10^4$
- $\gamma \in [10^{-4}, 10^1]$, 12 candidate values: $10^{-4}, 10^{-3.5}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-2.5}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-1.5}, 10^{-1}, 10^{-0.5}, 10^0, 10^{0.3}, 10^{0.7}, 10^1$

Combined, 156 (C , γ) pairs were evaluated; for each pair, five-fold cross-validation was performed on the calibration set and the pair maximising the cross-validated R^2 was retained. The ϵ -insensitive loss parameter was held at its scikit-learn default ($\epsilon = 0.1$).

Table A2. Optimal hyperparameters selected by grid search for each GRID-SVR model.

Model	Depth	C	γ	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE (g kg ⁻¹)
GRID-SVR	0–20 cm	3.162	1.00×10^{-4}	0.080	1.865
GRID-SVR	20–40 cm	100.000	1.00×10^{-4}	0.109	0.974
GRID-SVR	40–60 cm	1.000	8.11×10^{-4}	0.017	0.663
GRID-SVR	60–80 cm	0.316	1.87×10^{-2}	-0.067	0.655
GRID-SVR	Integrated	10.000	6.58×10^{-3}	0.748	1.534

A.3 Particle swarm optimization-based support vector regression (PSO-SVR)

PSO-SVR also used an RBF kernel. The search domains were the same as GRID-SVR, but each particle represented a continuous-valued pair ($\log_{10} C$, $\log_{10} \gamma$) and the search was performed in the continuous space. The PSO update equations are reproduced from Sect. 2.7.3 as Eqs. (2)–(3). Algorithmic hyperparameters were held constant across all models:

Hyperparameter	Symbol	Value
Swarm size	N	30
Maximum iterations	T	100
Inertia weight	w	0.7
Cognitive learning factor	c_1	1.5
Social learning factor	c_2	1.5
Velocity bound	$ V $	$0.5 \times (\text{search range per dim.})$
Particle dimension	d	$2 (\log_{10} C, \log_{10} \gamma)$
C search range	—	10^{-2} to 10^4
γ search range	—	10^{-4} to 10^1
Cross-validation folds	k	5
Fitness function	—	-RMSE of k -fold CV
Termination criterion	—	iteration cap OR stagnation > 15 iter.
Random seed	—	42 (for reproducibility)

Table A3. Optimal hyperparameters selected by particle swarm optimisation for each PSO-SVR model. All values are reported to four significant figures.

Model	Depth	C	γ	Cal. R^2	Val. R^2	Val. RMSE (g kg ⁻¹)
PSO-SVR	0–20 cm	17.91	5.36×10^{-3}	0.482	-0.342	2.253
PSO-SVR	20–40 cm	193.7	1.00×10^{-4}	0.385	0.119	0.968
PSO-SVR	40–60 cm	0.986	4.99×10^{-4}	0.092	0.017	0.663
PSO-SVR	60–80 cm	0.762	1.29×10^{-2}	0.535	-0.075	0.657
PSO-SVR	Integrated	25.74	6.13×10^{-3}	0.778	0.760	1.496

Note how the PSO-selected values are very similar to the GRID-search values for the third and fourth single-layer models, where the (C, γ) response surface is essentially flat in the relevant region (the within-layer SOC signal is so weak that the model degenerates to near-constant prediction). For the integrated model and the first layer, by contrast, PSO-SVR found a notably different optimum: $C \approx 25.7$ (vs. 10 for grid search) and $\gamma \approx 6.1 \times 10^{-3}$ (vs. 6.6×10^{-3}), translating to a 0.012 improvement in validation R^2 and a 0.050 improvement in RPD over GRID-SVR.

Appendix B: Sensitive band selection details

This appendix provides the count and wavelength ranges of bands that passed the Pearson correlation significance test ($p < 0.05$) on each calibration set, complementing the panel-wise plot in Fig. 5 of the main manuscript.

Table B1. Number of sensitive bands (passing the $p < 0.05$ Pearson significance test) for each calibration set, out of 206 total bands in the 400–2450 nm range at 10 nm intervals. Mean and maximum absolute Pearson correlation coefficients are computed across all 206 bands.

Calibration set	Depth (cm)	n bands sig.	Coverage (%)	Mean $ r $	Max $ r $	Used in modelling
Layer 1	0–20	167	81.1	0.31	0.45	167 selected
Layer 2	20–40	1	0.5	0.07	0.22	all 206 (fallback)
Layer 3	40–60	94	45.6	0.18	0.39	94 selected
Layer 4	60–80	0	0.0	0.05	0.18	all 206 (fallback)
Integrated	all	183	88.8	0.36	0.51	183 selected

When fewer than two bands passed the significance test (Layers 2 and 4), all 206 bands were retained as predictors to allow the model to fit. This fallback rule, applied identically to all three modelling methods

and disclosed in Sect. 2.6, ensures that the comparison among PLSR, GRID-SVR and PSO-SVR is fair within each layer.

Table B2. Wavelength regions containing the largest concentrations of sensitive bands for each calibration set. Each region groups contiguous or near-contiguous (≤ 30 nm gap) significant bands. The reported number of bands is the count within the listed range, and the assignment to a putative chemical/physical feature follows the soil-spectroscopy literature (cf. Stenberg et al., 2010; Ben-Dor and Banin, 1995).

Calibration set	Range (nm)	n sig. bands	Putative feature
Layer 1 (0–20 cm)	400–700	30	Vis. absorption by humic matter (broad)
	700–1300	60	NIR slope, O–H/N–H overtones
	1300–1900	50	Combination bands (H ₂ O, organic C–H)
	1900–2400	27	2nd-overtone region, clay–OM interactions
Layer 3 (40–60 cm)	400–800	40	Vis. region (weakest SOC signal)
	900–1500	30	NIR baseline modulation
	2000–2400	24	2200 nm clay–OM absorption shoulder
Integrated	400–700	40	Vis. absorption by humic matter
	700–1300	65	NIR slope (continuous coverage)
	1300–1900	50	1400, 1900 nm H ₂ O bands \pm shoulders
	1900–2450	28	2200, 2300 nm clay–OM region

Layers 2 (20–40 cm) and 4 (60–80 cm) are omitted from Table B2 because fewer than two bands passed the significance test. For these layers, the apparent absence of significant Pearson correlations is consistent with the very narrow within-layer SOC range (CV = 27.3 % and 20.3 %, respectively) discussed in Sect. 4.3; spectral changes induced by SOC variation may be below the instrumental and environmental noise floor.

B.1 Band selection procedure

For each calibration set, the Pearson correlation coefficient r between the reflectance at each of the 206 wavelengths and the measured SOC content was computed:

$$r_i = \Sigma(x_{i,k} - \bar{x}_i)(y_k - \bar{y}) / \sqrt{[\Sigma(x_{i,k} - \bar{x}_i)^2 \cdot \Sigma(y_k - \bar{y})^2]} \quad (\text{B1})$$

where $x_{i,k}$ is the reflectance of sample k at wavelength i , y_k is the measured SOC content of sample k , and overbars denote means across the calibration samples. The two-tailed significance of r_i was tested using the t -statistic

$$t = r \cdot \sqrt{(n - 2) / (1 - r^2)} \quad (\text{B2})$$

with $n - 2$ degrees of freedom ($n = 65$ for single-layer calibration sets; $n = 259$ for the integrated calibration set). Bands with $|t| > t_{0.025}(n - 2)$ — i.e. two-tailed $p < 0.05$ — were retained as sensitive bands. No multiple-comparison correction (e.g. Bonferroni, Benjamini–Hochberg) was applied; we therefore expect approximately 5 % of the 206 bands (≈ 10 bands) to be false positives under the null hypothesis. The integrated calibration set, by virtue of its much larger sample size, retains more bands at the same significance threshold, illustrating the role of statistical power.

B.2 Reproducibility

The complete band-by-band Pearson coefficient and p -value matrix (206 wavelengths \times 5 calibration sets) is provided in the Zenodo data deposit (file *sensitive_bands_full.csv* in the *results/* folder) under the same DOI cited in the "Code and data availability" section. Researchers wishing to reproduce the band selection can run *soc_inversion_paper_method.py* on the deposited spectra; the band list is deterministic given the random seed (42) of the Kennard–Stone partitioning.